

Multi-scale modeling of 2D GaSe FETs with strained channels

A. Toral-Lopez^{1,*}, H. Santos², E.G. Marin¹, F.G. Ruiz¹, J.J. Palacios³ and A. Godoy¹

¹ *Dpto. Electrónica y Tecnología de Computadores, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Granada (Spain)*

² *Dpto. Matemática Aplicada, Ciencia e Ingeniería de los Materiales y Tecnología Electrónica, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos (Spain)*

³ *Dpto. Física de la Materia Condensada, Condensed Matter Physics Center (IFIMAC), and Instituto Nicolás Cabrera (INC), Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Cantoblanco 28049, Spain*

* atoral@ugr.es

Abstract

Electronic devices based on bidimensional materials (2DMs) are the subject of an intense experimental research, that demands a tantamount theoretical activity. The latter must be hold up by a varied set of tools able to rationalize, explain and predict the operation principles of the devices. In the broad context of multi-scale computational nanoelectronics, there is currently a lack of simulation tools connecting atomistic descriptions with semi-classical mesoscopic device-level simulations and able to properly explain the performance of many state-of-the-art devices. To contribute to filling this gap we present a multi-scale approach that combines fine-level material calculations with a semi-classical drift-diffusion transport model. Its use is exemplified to assess 2DM-FET devices with strained channels, showing great potential to capture the changes in the crystal structure and their impact into the device performance. Interestingly, we verify the capability

of strain in monolayer GaSe to enhance the conduction of one type of carrier, enabling the possibility to mimic the effect of chemical doping on 2D materials. These results illustrate the great potential of the proposed approach to connect levels of abstraction rarely connected before and thus contribute to the theoretical modeling of state-of-the-art 2DM-based devices.

1 Introduction

In the unceasingly growing realm of bidimensional materials (2DMs), predictive simulation and modeling of nanoelectronic devices are key to perform early and low-cost exploration of the most auspicious paths for experimental investigation. At the same level of relevance than prediction within the theoretical activity, it is explanation, i.e. the rationalization and comprehension of those novel experimental findings that are not evident or fully understood. The duality between these activities is determined by the experimental progress, that sets a time frontier between them, with prediction looking at the future and explanation focusing on the present [1].

In the particular case of 2DM-based electronic devices this duality results, up to a certain point, in a dichotomy about the most appropriate theoretical framework for describing transport. Although the frontier is blurred, quantum approaches, exploiting in most cases non-equilibrium Green functions, are assumed to be the most adequate paradigm for anticipating the performance of novel concepts of devices; whereas semi-classical schemes, founded on diffusive transport, still hold the capability to better explain state-of-the-art realizations. Interestingly, while the former approach has been widely employed in a multi-scale scheme connecting device-level simulations with material atomistic calculations [2], the combination of semi-classical transport with an atomic-level description of the material properties remains mostly unexplored.

In this context, we propose a novel platform able to fill this gap within the semi-classical transport perspective, by connecting in a multi-scale fashion the material and device levels. Thus, we combine tight-binding (TB) calculations characterizing the material with a device-level description based on the continuity and Poisson equations. In particular, we describe

the material electronic structure through a position-dependent density of states (DoS), which is exploited in the calculation of the device-bias-dependent carrier statistics. In other words, we are able to describe the nanometric local changes in the crystal properties and incorporate them in mesoscopic semi-classical simulations of the device.

In order to exemplify the proposed approach, we have focused our attention on the evaluation of mechanical strain in 2DM-based devices [3, 4]. Strain engineering has already been widely employed in conventional silicon technology to boost carrier transport properties with a remarkable industrial success [5]. In fact, due to the inherent mechanical flexibility of 2D materials, it is expected to become a key technology enabling on-demand modulation of the optical, mechanical or electrical properties. As an example, it has been demonstrated that the application of controlled strain originates both, a noticeable enhancement of the photore-sponsivity of single-layer MoS₂ photodetectors [6], and modulates the Schottky barrier height of metal - TMDs contacts modifying the device transport properties [7]. In this work we focus on a particular subset of the 2D material family: metal monochalcogenides (MMs), and specifically on Gallium Selenide (GaSe) [8], in which the possibility of synthesizing monolayer wrinkled structures has opened the path to inhomogeneous strain yielding to spatially varying band structures at the nanoscale [9, 10, 11].

2 Multi-scale platform

The proposed platform combines TB calculations with device level drift-diffusion transport simulations. The TB model provides a detailed band-structure description of the investigated material, validated against Density Functional Theory (DFT) simulations (see Supporting Information). We must highlight that both DFT and TB result in a linear strain-band gap dependence differing only slightly in their predictions, with TB requiring a larger strain percentage to achieve the same bandgap modulation as in DFT. Nevertheless, the TB model is fully able to capture particular features arising from the conformal changes in the crystal structure produced by strain in monolayer GaSe and the corresponding position dependent DoS. This

implementation allows us to accurately include the effect of tensile or compressive strain with arbitrary patterns, such as those produced by substrate patterning or bubbling [9, 12], in the device level simulations so to achieve an accurate evaluation of the longitudinal carrier profiles in the framework of a drift-diffusion transport description.

2.1 Material level: tight binding description

Regarding material level TB calculations, We consider monolayer GaSe with different strain spatial profiles. As depicted in Figure 1, the unit cell of GaSe is composed by two Se and two Ga atoms disposed in the outer and inner cell, respectively. Their coordinates are $\text{Ga}(0,0,-b)$, $\text{Ga}(0,0,b)$, $\text{Se}(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{a\sqrt{3}}{2}, -c)$, and $\text{Se}(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{a\sqrt{3}}{2}, c)$, where $a = 2.25 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 1.27 \text{ \AA}$, and $c = 2.10 \text{ \AA}$. To form a layer the unit cell is repeated following the cell vectors $\vec{a}_1 = \frac{3a}{2} (1, \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}, 0)$ and $\vec{a}_2 = (0, a\sqrt{3}, 0)$.

Figure 1: (a) Illustration of crystal structure and zoom (b) the unit cell vectors. (c) Example of a tensile strained structure.

To model this system we employ nearest-neighbor TB Hamiltonian with four orbitals per atom (s , p_x , p_y and p_z). The Hamiltonian is given by

$$H = \sum_{i,j} t_{ij} c_i^\dagger c_j + c.c., \quad (1)$$

where t_{ij} is the nearest-neighbor hopping parameter and c_i^\dagger (c_j) the destruction (creation) operator. We have used the Camara *et. al.* TB parametrization [13] that was implemented for a 3D GaSe system. In order to fit the bands for a monolayer (2D system) we have corrected the

unit cell reducing the distance between Se atoms: this accounts for the fact that outer atoms do not interact with others atoms of adjacent layers, and therefore their distance is decreased. This changes softly the TB parameters and a Mexican hat shape for the first valence band is reached in very good agreement with DFT calculations. The bands structures exemplifying this along with DoS profiles can be found in the Supp. Info.

We have considered tensile and compressive strain in the zigzag (ZZ) direction, i.e. along \vec{a}_2 , having a 10% maximum strain with a soft cosine profile. We have considered supercells composed by 160 unit cells in this ZZ direction. This supercell is a box with four nearest-neighbor connection, with the following Hamiltonian:

$$H(k_{\parallel}, k_{\perp}) = H_{00} + H_{01}^{\parallel} e^{ik_{\parallel} \vec{a}_{\parallel}} + H_{10}^{\parallel} e^{-ik_{\parallel} \vec{a}_{\parallel}} + H_{01}^{\perp} e^{ik_{\perp} \vec{a}_{\perp}} + H_{10}^{\perp} e^{-ik_{\perp} \vec{a}_{\perp}} \quad (2)$$

where H_{00} is the supercell Hamiltonian, and H_{01} and H_{10} are the nearest-neighbor forward and backward hopping Hamiltonian, respectively. The box directions are indicated by parallel \parallel and perpendicular \perp symbols, and \vec{k} and \vec{a} represent the wavevector and real space vector for the box, respectively.

To calculate the DoS in systems with a big number of unit cells we have employed in one direction the Surface Green functions Matching Method [14, 15] being the local DoS $_l$

$$\text{DoS}_l(E, k_{\perp}) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \text{Im} [\text{Tr}(G_l(E, k_{\perp}))], \quad (3)$$

where G_l is the Green function of the cell l , and E the energy. The system is considered homogeneous in the direction perpendicular to the strained ZZ, therefore, k_{\perp} is a good quantum number. In that case, we can use the usual k -point summation techniques to evaluate the total DoS per unit cell:

$$\text{DoS}_l(E) = \frac{1}{N_{k_{\perp}}} \sum_{k_{\perp}=1}^{N_{k_{\perp}}} w_{k_{\perp}} \text{DoS}_l(E, k_{\perp}), \quad (4)$$

where w_{\perp} is the relative weight of each k_{\perp} . We have chosen $N_{k_{\perp}} = 130$ as the number of k_{\perp} ,

and a constant weight for each k_{\perp} , $w_{\perp} = 1$, in order to get a good approximation to the actual DoS. The final DoS profile depicts a spatial dependence in correspondence to the longitudinal position of the unit cells, y_l , and it is split into electron and hole DoS profiles as:

Figure 2: (a) Structures considered in the simulation of the Single-Gate (top) and Split-Gate (bottom) scenarios. Strain, tensile (T) or compressive (C), is applied to the access regions, i.e. regions not covered by the gates. (b) DoS profiles of the structures considered and (c) their respective longitudinal E_g profiles.

$$\text{DoS}_l(E) \begin{cases} \text{DoS}_l(E > E_g/2) = \text{DoS}_n(E, y_l) \\ \text{DoS}_l(E < E_g/2) = \text{DoS}_p(E, y_l) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

that are linearly interpolated in the 2D (E, y) space so to define the profiles $\text{DoS}_n(E, y)$ and $\text{DoS}_p(E, y)$, in the device simulations.

2.2 Device level: semi-classical numerical simulations

The simulation of the device encompasses the self-consistent solution of the Poisson equation along with the Continuity equation in a diffusive regime and the carrier statistics. The former

provides the potential profile in a 2D cross-section of the structure:

$$\nabla(\varepsilon \nabla V) = -\rho \quad (6)$$

where ε , V and ρ are the permittivity, potential and charge distributions, respectively. ρ includes the fixed charge associated to impurities or charged traps as well as electrons and holes. The continuity equation within a Drift-Diffusion description of the transport is written in terms of the pseudo-Fermi level gradients as [16]:

$$\nabla J_n = \nabla J_p = 0 \quad \text{with} \quad \begin{cases} J_n = q\mu_n n \nabla E_{F,n} \\ J_p = q\mu_p p \nabla E_{F,p} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where q is the electron charge, μ_n (μ_p) the electron (hole) mobility dependent on the longitudinal electric field [17], n (p) the electron (hole) longitudinal profile, J_n (J_p) the current density along the channel, and $E_{F,n}$ ($E_{F,p}$) the electron (hole) Fermi level profile.

The carrier statistics entering both in the Poisson and continuity equations are determined by the integral of DoS profiles obtained from the TB calculations weighted by the occupation probability dictated by the Fermi-Dirac function. Thus, the position dependent electron and hole densities are calculated as:

$$n(y) = \int_{E_i}^{\infty} \text{DoS}_n(E, y) f(E, E_{F,n}, E_C, y) dE \quad (8)$$

$$p(y) = \int_{-\infty}^{E_i} \text{DoS}_p(E, y) [1 - f(E, E_{F,p}, E_V, y)] dE$$

where E_i , E_C and E_V stand for the intrinsic, conduction band minimum and valence band maximum energies, respectively, and f the Fermi function. The spatial profiles of the pseudo-Fermi levels as well as the potential are involved in these expressions; the latter defining the conduction and valence bands, requiring a self-consistent evaluation of Equations (6), (7) and (8) until convergence is achieved.

3 Results

In order to illustrate the capabilities of the proposed approach, we have considered the 2D-field-effect-transistor configurations shown in Figure 2a. In these devices the channel regions are relaxed (i.e. without strain), while the strain (tensile or compressive) is applied in those areas not covered by the gate, i.e. the access regions. In particular, four devices are evaluated, corresponding to two geometries, Single-Gate (SG) and Split-Gate (SPG) FETs with both, n-type and p-type conductivity channels. Gate lengths are set to cover the relaxed semiconductor regions and so that, $L_g = 20.27\text{nm}$ (52 unit cells) for the SG devices, and $L_g = 11.69\text{nm}$ (30 unit cells) for the SPG devices. In addition, devices with completely relaxed channel are used as references. In this way, concurrently to the demonstration of the proposed platform, we assess the role of the strain to enhance the conductivity of the access regions, and thus as potential alternative to other approaches based on: locally gated devices [18, 19]; self-aligned gate contacts [20, 21]; locally charged insulators [22]; phase changes [23, 24]; or chemical doping [25, 26].

As previously stated, the GaSe monolayer is $160|\vec{a}_2|$ -long corresponding to 62.3nm in the relaxed devices. This length slightly changes according to the type of strain and the number of strained regions considered (see Supp. Info.). In all cases the channel and access regions total dimension is extended by two 5nm-long regions with a high conductivity that emulate the source and drain contacts and determine the polarity of the device. Despite the importance of contacts in the context of 2DM-based FETs [27, 28, 29, 30, 7], we try to analyze the impact of the applied strain on the device performance, avoiding other effects that could overshadow it. Finally, a 10nm-thick HfO_2 layer covers the GaSe channels acting as gate insulator.

The DoS profiles corresponding to the different GaSe strained crystals are depicted in Figure 2b along with the local variations in the energy gap (E_g), Figure 2c. The relaxed material shows $E_g = 1.42\text{ eV}$. This value is close to the DFT gap, but smaller than the experimental one since we are using TB parameters designed for bulk. In any case, this does not affect our results as the strain-gap relation from TB requires larger strain values to achieve the same gap variation

Figure 3: Transfer characteristics (top) and transconductance (bottom) of the SG structures. In all the cases we consider both n-type (a,c) and p-type (b,d) transistors to evaluate how strain impacts on the conduction of each type of carrier.

in contrast with the relation obtained from DFT results.

The compressive/tensile strain tends to increase/decrease the band gap, in good agreement with similar trends reported in the literature [11, 9, 31]. In particular, the strain-engineered control of the bandgap in GaSe nanosheets has been experimentally demonstrated in [12], with substantial decrease/increase in the energy gap (measured by exciton energy extraction) upon the application of uniaxial tensile/compressive strain.

These DoS profiles nurture the mesoscopic device self-consistent simulations resulting in the transfer characteristics of the SG FETs operating as both n-type (left) and p-type (right) devices depicted in Figure 3. The strain has a noticeable impact on the conduction performance of n-type and p-type SG devices. Tensile strain (T2) enhances the electron conduction and degrades the hole current, while compressive strain (C2) results on the opposite behavior. It is therefore evident that the application of strain on the access regions produces an effect similar to the chemical doping, promoting the conduction of one specific type of carrier.

This induced-doping strain relation has been evidenced for other 2D materials, such as black-phosphorus (BP) [32] where strain-modulated bandgap significantly alters the density of

thermally activated carriers, impacting the conductance of BP-based FETs; and in single-layer MoS₂ [33] where experimental evidence of the direct relation between strain and doping has been shown by Raman mapping and electrical measurements.

The local doping results in a relevant increase in the output current and transconductance (Figure 3c and 3d) by a twofold factor, with respect to the relaxed case, is observed when the appropriate strain is employed, i.e. tensile (compressive) for n-type (p-type) operation. These changes can be associated to an increase in the carrier density in the access regions due to the strain (Figure S6). A trend to saturation of the transfer response is observed for large gate voltages regardless the strain condition, explained by the bias-independent fixed conductivity of these regions.

Figure 4: Left plots show the transfer response of the n-type devices (a,c) and p-type devices (b,d) for the SPG-1 configuration, i.e. $V_G = V_{g1}$ and $V_{ctr} = V_{g2}$. $V_{DS} = 0.1V$ in all the scenarios. Strained devices correspond to the top panel and the relaxed ones to the bottom one. Right plots show the evolution of the main carrier concentrations when $V_G = V_{g1}$ and $V_{ctr} = V_{g2}$. (e) and (g) plots correspond to the device with tensile strain (n-type), and right column (f) and (h) plots correspond to the device with compressive strain (p-type).

Next, we extend this analysis to the Split-Gate (SPG) devices shown in Figure 2a, taking advantage of the versatility of the proposed platform. This type of structures are appealing for non-linear applications, such as mixers [34], or to implement different functionalities, such as logic gates, with a reduced number of transistors [35]. For the sake of relevance, we limit

the investigation to tensile n-type and compressive p-type conduction. To analyze the SPG device operation we set one gate performing a whole sweeping cycle V_G while the other acts as a control input V_{ctr} . Figure 4 shows the transfer responses for the SPG-1 configuration, i.e., ($V_G = V_{g1}$, $V_{\text{ctr}} = V_{g2}$), where $V_{\text{DS}} = 0.1\text{V}$ for all the scenarios considered. A similar study for the SPG-2 configuration (i.e. $V_G = V_{g2}$, $V_{\text{ctr}} = V_{g1}$) can be found in Figure S7.

Figure 4a-d evidences that also in the SPG-FETs the output current (along with the transconductance in Figure S8) is enhanced by the application of strain in the access regions. A saturated trend is observed in all cases. It should be highlighted, however, that this behavior is originated not only by the strained access regions, but also by the channel under the control gate which has a fixed conductivity. This is confirmed by the carrier density profiles depicted in Figure 4e-h, where small fluctuations in the carrier density in that channel are observed when V_{g1} is swept.

Figure 5 extends the SPG-FET analysis to the $I_{\text{on}}/I_{\text{off}}$ ratio as a function of the control gate bias, V_{ctr} . A low power specification has been considered, that is $I_{\text{Off}} = 10^{-4}\mu\text{A}/\mu\text{m}$ and $V_{\text{On}} = V_{\text{Off}} \pm 0.3\text{V}$. Figure 5 reveals that the ON-OFF ratio is notably enhanced for the structures with strained access regions and it can be notably modulated by the control gate, the larger the conductivity of this region the better the resulting ON-OFF ratio in both p-type and n-type operation. Finally, it is also notable the differences in the ON-OFF ratio when the control gate is interchanged. The gate closer to the drain contact (V_{g2}) is able to modulate the ON-OFF ratio to a larger extent than V_{g1} .

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, we have presented a novel multi-scale numerical platform able to connect a fine-level description of strained 2D materials (based on TB calculations validated against DFT results, although the method is not restricted to it and can be applicable to DoS profiles extracted directly from DFT) with a semi-classical diffusive simulation of FET devices through the self-consistent solution of the continuity and Poisson equations. To exemplify the proposed

Figure 5: On-Off ratio of the SPG devices as a function of the control bias. The calculation of these values follows the Low-Power compliance: $I_{\text{Off}} = 10^{-4} \mu\text{A}/\mu\text{m}$, $V_{\text{On}} = V_{\text{Off}} \pm 0.3\text{V}$ according to [36].

approach, we exploit the position dependent DoS in the calculation of the device carrier statistics, by considering two FET configurations: a Single-Gate and a Split-Gate transistor, along with different types of applied strain. The obtained results show that this approach is suitable to capture the impact of the strain on the device electrical performance. It is observed that a properly engineered local strain could help to mitigate the negative impact of access regions and to control the polarity of the device, mimicking the effect of chemically doped 2D crystals coherently with the first experimental evidences demonstrating this strain-induced doping relation in 2DMs.

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Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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